

**A STUDY OF THE READING AND STUDY HABITS OF ENGLISH
LEARNERS OF STD VII****Dr. Sr. Tanuja Waghmare**

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Every man who knows how to read has it in his power to magnify himself, to multiply the ways, in which he exists, to make his life full, significant and interesting.

Aldous Huxely

It is an adage that individuals are not born with innate desire to perform any action in their environment. According to philosophers human beings are like a clean slate. As soon as the child works mutually with his milieu, the experiences leave ineradicable impressions on the mind of the child. The instruction received in school enables the child to bring out the latent abilities that one has but it cannot create anything new. Teaching and learning helps one to grow from within oneself more rapidly and effortlessly and one of education's dependable and reliable servants that help in the development is 'habit'. W. James thinks that the nurturing of proper habits is the aim of edification. Habits according to him are the 'Flywheels of Society'.

Hull who is of the pure behaviouristic idea says that a habit is the blend of stimulus – response which is reinforced by some reward or punishment. When one acts in a routine manner doing a particular action daily it becomes a habit. Generally speaking there are good habits and bad habits. An individual requires to put in tremendous effort to form good habits. The parents, siblings and relations play an important part in the development of habits. These fine and superior habits come gradually and naturally they are easy to retain whereas bad habits require no labour at all. In these circumstances good habits are to be preserved and bad habits should be avoided. As the well known proverb says "Practiced in youth, accomplished in age".

The temperament of a person is usually gaged by his habits and, habits are the very essence of the soul. The skill to form habits is the most prominent and useful trait of a human being, whether we see him as a baby, youngster or a grown up person. The saying is apt "the sapling is bent – the tree is inclined".

The dwelling place of a child has great importance in the life of a child, it is here that they emulate whatever they see. The parents train the child in study habits for the growth and improvement of the child. This is further enhanced, developed and motivated in the school which is the second place of learning. Hence these two social agencies must provide ample opportunities for the child to form good habits as they exercise an immense influence on the education of a child.

Globalization and technology have had a great impact in the 21st century. In this era attainment and efficiency is the key word. For the students to scale to great heights they need to excel in their educational field. The children are influenced by the environment and especially all the new trends that have always enveloped the students. They need to keep themselves abreast by what is happening around them. It is a well known fact that what is seen is learnt better and finally studied.

The learner faces the vast ocean of knowledge and also of cut throat competition. It has been observed by the researcher that the learner puts in their best to study well, they attend classes and coaching classes but

fall short of meeting the expectations of their parents and teachers. To a great extent this reflects on the poor and incorrect study habits of the children.

Good study habits are very vital in the process of self learning. It is also important for success in school, college and higher education. Study habits should aim at nourishing the mind not on exercising it. One cannot conclude and say that good study habits mean hard work and reading hours together but it certainly means making up time for learning and revising. Many children have the capacity to work hard but lack suitable study habits.

As John Dryden has rightly said,, “ We first make our habits, and then our habits make us”.

Success is a habit. Failure and mediocrity are also habits. An individual needs to ask oneself which habits does one prefer to dominate in one’s life? The intellect is a very authoritative “answer engine”. It will always find answers to questions we ask it. If you make a commitment to search for success and make habits out of the things that work for you, you’ll be amazed at how many answers and solutions will seem to just appear in front of you.

If one really desires contentment and remarkable occasions to achieve success in life then Kaizen, constant enthusiasm and passion has the power to create that success.

Kaizen is famous as one of the foundation stones of the success of the Japanese industry. It is a principle that demands steady progress everyday. Achievement will not come at once one should commit oneself to find ways and means to improve every day. It is the amassing of these little steps that creates the biggest change. It is the unswerving application of this principle that creates lasting change.

Success becomes a habit and it keeps scaling upwards. Success with schoolwork and learning is no different. It is an exciting insight that one can learn anything and even more stimulating to prove it to oneself over and over again.

In the long run, success for students depends on the scholastic achievements. Therefore, effective study skills schematically develop a student’s personal success in studies, examination and most of all in life.

In the present research a study has been made on the study habits and reading habits with respect to the English language and to see how independent the learner is. Thus enabling the students to improve their study habits and reading habits.

Statement of the problem:

A study of the reading and study habits of English learners of std VII.

Aim of the study:

To study the reading and study habits of English learners of std VII.

Objectives of the study:

- To study the study habits of students of std VII with respect to the English language.
- To check the independent nature of students of std VII with respect to the learning of English language.
- To check the awareness of the reading habits of the students of std VII with respect to the English language.

Methodology of the study:

For the present study the researcher has used descriptive research design wherein the survey method has been used to study the reading and study habits of the students of Std. VII.

Sample size and its nature:

For the present study, the researcher collected data from the students of std VII. The total sample was 62. The sample was limited to English medium students. The sample included only girls. Convenient sampling technique was used to study the reading and study habits of the students of Std VII.

Tool used for the study:

The data was collected by using a “Questionnaire on Study and Reading Habits”. This tool had three dimensions:

- A. What kind of an English learner are you?
- B. Are you an independent English learner?
- C. What are good reading habits?

Analysis and interpretation of data:

The researcher made use of descriptive analysis technique to analyze the obtained data. It included graphical representation of the obtained data.

Data Analysis:

Objective 1: To study the study habits of students of std VII with respect to the English language.

Score	Description	Responses of the students
30-40	You are an active and serious English learner. You try your best to learn English well and are willing to do extra work. Good! You are on the right track. Keep it up.	2
19-29	You are a hard working student and like to follow instruction. You can do even better if you can make better use of the other resources more! Set your study plan and work on it.	24
10-18	You are not an effective English learner. You need to form some good habits in English learning and need to spend much more time doing things in English.	34
Below 10	You are a poor English learner. You need to form good habits in English learning. Maybe you are afraid of learning English. Maybe you don't know how to learn English well. Don't worry. Set your study plan. Set a goal and start work. You can have lots of improvement.	2

It was found that 3% students possess good study habits, 39% students could do better, 55% students needed help and 3% students possess poor study habits.

Objective 2: To check the independent nature of students of std VII with respect to the learning of English language.

Score	Description	Response of the students
18-24	You are quite an independent English learner. You learn how to use English. Keep using English you learnt in your schoolwork and daily life. Then you can learn even better.	29
8-16	You can be an independent English learner. You have formed some good habits in learning English. Now you have to use more English references and practice all that is required to improve in English. Then work hard on them.	33
0-6	You depend on your English teacher quite a lot and want to be told what to do. If you want to learn English well, you need to use reference books and be much more active in learning English. Prepare well for the English class and spend more time on English activities. Then work hard on them.	nil

It was found that 53% students are in the category of ‘can be an independent English learner’ and 47% students fall in the category of ‘quite an independent English learner’.

Objective 3: To check the awareness of the reading habits of the students of std VII with respect to the English language.

Score	Description	Response of the students
9-12	You are well aware of good reading habits with respect to English Language	5
5-8	You have an average awareness of good reading habits with respect to English Language	48
Below 5	You lack awareness of good reading habits with respect to English Language	9

It was found that 8% students had good awareness of good reading habits with respect to English Language, 77% students had average awareness of good reading habits with respect to English Language whereas 15% students had poor awareness of good reading habits with respect to English Language.

Findings of the study:

- 3% students had good study habits, 39% students could do better, 55% of students needed help and 3% of students were poor in their study habits.
- 53% students fall in the category of ‘can be an independent English learner’ and 47% students fall in the ‘quite an independent English learner’.
- It was found that 8% students had good awareness of good reading habits with respect to English Language, 77% students had average awareness of good reading habits with respect to English Language whereas 15% students had poor awareness of good reading habits with respect to English Language.

Conclusion:

Due to the advancement of technology the use of computers and mobile have deteriorated the reading habits of the students. This is a pathetic state to see that the students studying in an English medium school need a lot of improvement in their study habits and reading habits. They need to be given coaching and special attention.

The students need to be encouraged:

- to speak only in English in the class as well as outside the classroom
- to read stories or other books in English
- to write to a pen-friend in English
- to read English newspapers
- to do extra English grammar exercises daily
- to spend at least 2 hours working on English everyday.

To top the above said points the students could be introduced to e-library.

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**ANALYTICAL STUDY OF VARIOUS STORAGE FACILITIES WITH
REFERENCE TO AGRICULTURE PRODUCE OF THE FARMERS,
RETAILERS AND COMMISSION AGENTS**

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Introduction:

Storage is a source of which increase benefit to the all types of respondents whether it is farmer, retailer or commission agent which further gives the more benefit of the high returns for the Agri produce. Hence the researcher is interested to find out the various storage facilities with reference to agriculture produce in Nanded district.

Research Methodology of the study:

In order to collect the primary data following methodology has been adopted. The investigation in economics starts with selection of appropriate numbers of respondent's preparation of scheduled selection of proper tools of analysis for the collection of data. Details regarding the plan of investigation i.e. sampling design, nature & sources of data, Statistical tools & Techniques etc. adopted for the study are presented in this paper under the following heads:

Sampling design:

Since the study has aimed at finding out the storage facilities with reference to agriculture produce in Nanded district, the sample for the study necessarily involves the selection of cultivators as well as marketing intermediaries for gathering relevant data on the above aspects of the study.

In this study for the selection of cultivators multistage sampling techniques have been followed with district as the first unit, tehsils as the second unit and villages as the third and final unit.

Selection of district:

The agro climatic conditions prevailing in Nanded district of the Marathwada region in Maharashtra state are congenial for agriculture. Similarly, there is a good network of canals in the district, which enables to increase water table of the wells in the command area of the canals. This offers good scope for agriculture development. Hence, Nanded district has been selected purposively for the present study.

Selection of tehsils:

There are sixteen tehsils in Nanded District and all the talukas are selected as samples for the present study.

Selection of villages:

In this study, five villages from each taluka are selected randomly. These total samples villages are 80 from sixteen talukas have been selected for the present study.

Selection of farmers:

20 farmers from each taluka totaling 320 have been selected randomly (purposive random selection method). The list of farmers of selected villages has been obtained from the land holding.

Selection of markets:

Agricultural Production in Nanded district is marketed either in Nanded or Hyderabad market. Hence, the researcher has been selected as market of the production area and the latter as market of the consuming area.

Selection of market functionaries:

From Nanded market 10 commission agents and 30 retailers and 2 commission agents and 10 retailers from each taluka level market have been selected randomly. The Primary cross sections data have been collected by the survey method through conducting personal interviews of head of the respondent family. The data have been gathered with the help of well-structured specially designed pre-tested schedules separately for agriculture crop cultivators and each marketing functionary involved in the problems & prospectus of agriculture.

Objective of the study:

To identify the various storage facilities with reference to agriculture produce of the farmers, retailers and commission agents in Nanded district.

Hypothesis of the study:

In-depth qualitative rather than quantitative information was used for the purpose to answer the research questions. Farmers, Retailers and the commission agents were interviewed to gather information.

Following is the hypothesis of the present study.

Farmers, retailers and commission agents of Nanded district are facing the problem of storage facilities with reference to agriculture produce.

Statistical Tools & Techniques:

The following tools are used for analysis and interpretation of the study as wherever they are suitable / applicable.

- A. Percentages
- B. Ratios
- C. Growth Rates
- D. Chi-Square Analysis
- E. Figures

Storage Facilities with the respondents:

Storage is a source of which increase benefit to the all types of respondents whether it is farmer, retailer or commission agent which further gives the more benefit of the high returns for the Agri produce.

TABLE
STORAGE FACILITIES WITH THE RESPONDENTS

Sr. No.	Storage Facilities	No. of Respondents			Total	%
		Farmers	Retailers	Commission Agents		
01	House	247	64	09	320	59.26
02	Cold Storage	12	53	08	73	13.51
03	Godowns	23	51	12	86	15.93
04	Neighbor	38	12	11	61	11.30
Total		320	180	40	540	100.00

Source: - Field Survey

($X^2=151.67$, table value @ 5% level = 12.6)

Since the immemorial time house has been the main source of storage of food grains to farmers. As presented in table, 320 respondents surveyed use own house as their storage out of which 247 are farmers, 64 retailers and 9 commission agents which aggregated 59.26%. Cold storage house has attracted a little to the farmers, retailers and commission agents where 73 respondents stores their agri produce out of which 12 farmers, 53 retailers and 8 commission agents which aggregated 13.51% of total produce. In godown 15.93% of agri produce stores wherein 23 farmers, 51 retailers and 12 commission agents are stores their agri produce. Some of farmers, retailers and commission agents use their neighboring houses; godowns etc. to store their agri produce which is small in number grossly aggregating 11.30% wherein 38 farmers, 12 retailers and 11 commission agents.

Testing of Hypothesis:

From the calculations based on the above table, calculated value of Chi-Square is worked out as 16.71 whereas Table Value at 5% degree of freedom is 12.6. Calculated value of Chi-Square is more than the table value. Therefore the hypothesis is rejected.

Conclusion:

It can be said that the farmers, retailers and commission agents of Nanded district are not facing the problem of storage facilities with reference to agriculture produce.